

Special Relativity, Frame Motion and the Speed of Light

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One may derive special relativity for a particle with rest mass, by considering a particle at rest which is seen to have a velocity v (vector) when viewed from a frame moving with a velocity $-v$. In other words, there may be a physical moving frame as seen from the lab which is accountable for the particle's velocity. In particular, such a treatment leads to the Lorentz transformation and the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ which is also the free particle relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action if $v = x/t$.

Interestingly, the invariants of special relativity (and the Lorentz transformation) developed for a particle with rest mass apply to the photon. A photon has no rest mass (and hence there is no rest frame) and its velocity c in a vacuum is the same whether viewed in a lab or from a moving frame. This does not mean, however, that there is no concept of relative velocity. If a moving frame, such as a mirror or interface with a different index of refraction, exists, the concept of a relative velocity is fine (as seen in a lab frame). Given that v for a particle with rest mass may be applied to a moving frame, it seems there is no reason for this definition not to apply in the photon case. Thus, $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = -t |\mathbf{p}| (E/|\mathbf{p}| + \text{unit vector} \cdot \mathbf{r}/t)$ where the unit vector is in the direction of \mathbf{p} (momentum). In the photon case, $-\mathbf{r}/t$ vector may be considered to be the velocity of the moving mirror or medium interface. How does the photon velocity in a vacuum appear? We argue that it is a solution which leaves $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ unchanged, i.e. there is a velocity such that $0 = t (-E + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x}/t)$. Here \mathbf{p} is taken to be in the x direction and so $E = |\mathbf{p}|c$, the photon dispersion relationship.

Thus $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ is associated with two velocities for a photon. As argued in (1), if one considers the moving mirror/interface velocity, one may have a constant Lagrangian (called a phase/ t for the photon wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$). One may equate: $|\mathbf{p}| (E/|\mathbf{p}| + \text{unit vector} \cdot \mathbf{r}/t)$ for an incident ray to a reflected and refracted ray.

Alternatively $-E + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}/t$ is associated with a Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass. Such a transformation is like a type of rotation in 4-space. We argue that the scalar $A = t * (\text{relative velocity along the photon ray})$ is related to the motion of a physical mirror or interface of media. We suggest there exists a conserved hypothetical velocity (2) along the surface of the interface and that the relative velocity along the photon ray is a projection of this.

Special Relativity for a Particle with Rest Mass

The Lorentz transformation and Lorentz invariants are most easily seen in the case of a particle with a rest mass because it has a rest frame (unlike the photon). Consider a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at time t . If there exists another frame, quite possibly a physical one and not simply a theoretical consideration, moving with velocity $-v$ (not necessarily constant), then from the point of view of this frame, the particle is moving with velocity v . This means that $x=0$, t should be seen as x', t' in the new frame such that:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((1))$$

This allows one to develop a unitary transformation:

$$|x'\rangle = |f(v) f(v)v| |x\rangle \quad ((2))$$

$$|t'\rangle = |-f(v)v f(v)| |t\rangle$$

$$\text{Unitarity gives: } f(v)f(v) (1-vv) = 0 \text{ so } f(v) = \text{sqrt}(1-vv) \quad ((3))$$

Actually one needs v/b where b is a constant with units of velocity. The above transformation may also be applied to (p,E) , it is assumed. In such a case, $E = m_0 b / \text{sqrt}(1-vv/bb)$ and $p = m_0 v / \text{sqrt}(1-vv/bb)$

A Lorentz invariant of this transformation is:

$$A = -Et + p \cdot r \quad ((4))$$

At this point, the arguments only hold for a particle with rest mass. A photon, however, has an E and p and is associated with r (vector) and t . If ((3)) and ((4)) are to hold for a photon as well,, they should be consistent with $E=pc$ which follows from $A=0 \rightarrow c = x/t = E/p$. This leads to $b = c$. $A=0$, however, does not yield the velocity for a particle with rest mass, even though its velocity is also x/t , but A is not 0. The particle's velocity exists because of the moving physical frame.

Moving Physical Frame and a Photon

A photon in a vacuum has the same velocity c as seen from different frames. Unlike a particle with rest mass, it does not assume its velocity because it is seen from a physical moving frame. A physical moving frame, such as a mirror or medium interface, may exist in a problem. In such a case, the moving frame should be interpreted as having a speed $-v$ where $v = x/t$ in $A = -Et + px$, with A not 0. $A=0$ means that for a photon there exists a second velocity in the problem, $x/t = E/p$, which does not change A .

For a particle with rest mass,

$$A = -Et + p \cdot r = \text{classical action (relativistically and nonrelativistically)} \quad ((5))$$

In the nonrelativistic case, $E = p^2/2m_0$ and $p = mv$. The classical action is closely associated with the movement of the particle.

The classical action is equivalent to: Lagrangian * t and is a constant for a constant v , i.e. $tp^2/2m_0$ nonrelativistically and $-m_0 t \text{sqrt}(1-vv/cc)$ relativistically. If the Lagrangian is also a constant for a photon in a problem with a moving mirror or medium interface, then:

$$A = (\text{relative velocity}) * t = t |p| (-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t) \quad ((6)) \text{ where the unit vector is in the direction of } p.$$

Here, r/t vector is minus the velocity of the moving object, i.e. mirror or medium interface. $A/(-t)$ is a constant which is the same for incident, reflected and refracted photon rays.

There is, however, an alternative geometric interpretation because $(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t)$ is a relative velocity along the photon ray as seen in the lab frame, with $E/|p| = c/n$. The relative velocity is one involving the photon speed c/n and the projection of $-v$ vector along the ray direction. We argue as in (2) that there is a constant hypothetical velocity whose projection along the photon ray is this relative velocity or piece of the Lorentz invariant $-Et + p \cdot r$. In other words, there is the sense of a kind of 4-space rotation associated with $-Et + p \cdot r = |p|(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t)$.

((6)) may now be applied to various physical problems as noted in (1)

Examples

Snell's Law

In the case of Snell's law, there is no moving interface, only a static one, namely an interface of two media with different indices of refraction. In such a case: dr/dt vector is 0 so ((6)) yields:

$E = \text{constant in each medium. ((7))}$

The incident and reflected photon have the same E . This does not solve the problem, one needs two extra pieces of information. The first is that c/n is the speed of light in a medium, which is an experimental observable. The second makes use of Newtonian ideas of force, impulse. One may suggest that the component of momentum parallel to the surface of the interface does not undergo an impulse hit. Consider an interface lying along the x axis, with n_1 above and n_2 below. Then:

$p_1 \sin(AA) = p_2 \sin(BB)$ and $E=E$ so $p_1 c/n_1 = p_2/cn_2$ ((8))

One may note that even though there is no impulse along the x axis, the speed of light component along the x axis differs ie. $c/n_1 \sin(AA) \neq c/n_2 \sin(BB)$. Here AA is the incident angle measured from the y axis and BB the refracted, also measured from the y axis. As shown the speed of light in a vacuum c is a solution of $A=0$ which is different from the $A \neq 0$ case.

Combining ((8)) with $E=E$ yields Snell's law.

Reflection from a Moving Mirror or Refraction from a Moving Interface

One may consider a mirror, lying along the x -axis, moving with $-v$ along the y axis. In such a case, there is a physical frame (the mirror) moving with a velocity and one may use the full form of ((6)). Thus:

$|p \text{ incident}| (-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t) = \text{incident relative velocity}$ ((9a))

$|p \text{ reflected}| (-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t) = \text{reflected relative velocity}$ ((9b))

With $((9a) = ((9b))$

Unit vector dot $r/t = v \cos(AA)$ (incident) and unit vector dot $r/t = -v \cos(BB)$ reflected .

$((9a))= ((9b))$ already yields an equation, If one introduces conservation of momentum along the surface of the moving object, then:

$$|p \text{ incident}| \sin(AA) = |p \text{ reflected}| \sin(BB) \quad ((9c))$$

$$((9a))= ((9b)) \text{ then reads as: } \sin(AA) / \sin(BB) = (c - \cos(AA)v) / (c + \cos(BB)v).$$

If one has refraction instead of reflection,, $E/|p|$ in the numerator is replaced with $c/n1$ and in the denominator with $c/n2$.

Alternatively, one may use a geometrical approach with a hypothetical velocity H which lies along the surface of the moving object and is conserved.

Using $H \sin(AA) = (-c + \text{unit vector dot } r/t)$ and $H \sin(BB) = (-c - \text{unit vector dot } r/t)$ so:

$$\sin(AA) / \sin(BB) = (-c + \text{unit vector dot } r/t) / (-c - \text{unit vector dot } r/t) \quad ((10))$$

In other words, the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + p \text{ dot } r$ written in terms of a physical velocity in a problem involving a photon, may be written in terms of the photon relative velocity, i.e. $A \neq 0$. The relative velocity along the photon ray is a projection of a constant hypothetical velocity H which lies along the surface of the moving medium, i.e. is perpendicular to the r/t vector

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that special relativity (i.e. Lorentz transformations) may be derived for a particle with rest mass because it has a rest frame. The particle obtains a velocity vector v if seen from a physically moving frame with velocity $-v$. This leads to the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + p \text{ dot } r$, which is also the classical relativistic and nonrelativistic free particle action. A may be written in terms of the velocity of the moving frame, $t|p|(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector } dr/dt)$ where $-dr/dt$ is the velocity of the moving frame, and the unit vector is along p .

We argue that this also holds for light. In the case of a photon, however, there are two velocities. First, $-r/t$ represents a physical moving object, such as a mirror or medium interface and $A \neq 0$. Secondly, if $A=0$, there is a velocity $x/t = E/p$ which is the photon speed in a vacuum. It holds for any frame as long as one uses E' and p' in that frame, but the Lorentz transformations show that for a vacuum, this value is the constant c .

We further argue that one may apply $B = |p|(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector } dr/dt)$ to a photon interacting with a moving object as it is the same constant for an incident ray, reflected ray and refracted ray. Note: for a photon $E/|p| = c/n$.

Alternatively, one may use a geometric approach linked with relative velocity. We suggest that there exists a constant hypothetical velocity H (2) along the surface of the mirror and that B is its

projection. In other words, B which is linked with a kind of 4-rotation is also equivalent to relative velocity along the photon ray. This then allows one to solve reflection/refraction from both a stationary surface and a moving one by using:

$$\frac{H\sin(AA)}{H\sin(BB)} = \frac{(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector } dr/dt)_{\text{incident}}}{(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector } dr/dt)_{\text{reflected/refracted}}}$$

Here unit vector is along p incident or p reflected/refracted.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Hypothetical Velocity and Photon Ray Theory for Reflection/Refraction from a Moving Surface Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2023)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fermat's Principle and a Hypothetical Velocity Hypotenuse Approach (preprint, zenodo, 2022)